

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF Re COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ_m^{**} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
	Re	N	Cl/SO ₄	
[ReOOH(Big) ₂]	43.90 (44.42)	33.05 (33.39)	-	-
[ReOCl(Big) ₂]	43.32 (42.54)	32.17 (31.98)	8.20 (8.09)	-
[ReOCl(BigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	35.81 (36.47)	27.48 (27.41)	20.42 (20.82)	324 ^{a, c}
[ReCl ₂ (BigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	32.24 (32.93)	24.84 (24.75)	31.54 (31.34)	330 ^b
[Re(OH) ₂ (BigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂ ²	34.70 (35.23)	26.45 (26.48)	19.92 (20.11)	340 ^a
[ReO(OH)(MeBig) ₂]	41.34 (41.64)	31.30 (31.30)	-	-
[ReOCl(MeBig) ₂]	38.76 (39.99)	30.19 (30.06)	7.54 (7.61)	-
[ReOCl(MeBigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	34.24 (34.57)	26.36 (25.99)	19.45 (19.74)	320 ^{a, c}
[ReCl ₂ (MeBigH) ₂] ₂ Cl ₂	30.56 (31.37)	23.25 (23.58)	29.41 (29.86)	325 ^b
[Re(BigH) ₂](SO ₄) _{1.5} · 7H ₂ O ^d	24.25 (24.52)	27.83 (27.65)	18.94 (18.96)	-

*Big = Biguanide, MeBig = methyl biguanide; ^d% loss at 120°: Found 16.20 (Calcd. 16.59).

**In solvent: ^awater, ^bMeOH; ^chydrolysed.

the protonated form offers bidentate chelation and all the six coordination sites are occupied by biguanide nitrogen atom.

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Mechanism of Oxidation of Propan-1-ol and Butan-1-ol by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III) using Ruthenium(VIII) Oxide as a Homogeneous Catalyst

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OSMIUM tetroxide catalysed oxidation of methanol and ethanol by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) was first reported by Krishna and Singh¹ along with the oxidation of mandalate ion². Recently, osmium tetroxide has been replaced by ruthenium tetroxide and its catalytic activity was studied by Tandon and Krishna³. Ruthenium(VIII) oxide has been reported to catalyse the oxidation of diols by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III)⁴, but the oxidation of alcohols catalysed by ruthenium(VIII)

NOTES

oxide is still unknown. Moreover, ruthenium compounds have been found to be important from industrial and technical point of view⁵. Therefore, in the present study we have carried out the oxidation of propan-1-ol and butan-1-ol by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) using ruthenium(VIII) oxide as a homogeneous catalyst.

Experimental

Stock solutions of alcohols (Riedel), potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) (E. Merck) and other solutions (either AnalaR or chemically pure substances) were prepared. Ruthenium(VIII) oxide (Johnson Matthey) was dissolved in alkaline solution and the final strengths of catalyst and alkali were kept $3.025 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $0.135 M$, respectively. Reactions were carried out at constant temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The progress of the reaction was monitored at different intervals of time by estimating the amount of hexacyanoferrate(II) produced by titrating it against the standard solution of ceric sulphate using ferroin as a redox indicator. In all the kinetic runs alcohol was present in excess.

Results and Discussion

Ruthenium(VIII) oxide catalysed oxidation of propan-1-ol and butan-1-ol was studied at constant ionic strength under the conditions where uncatalysed reaction was negligible.

Table 1 shows that calculated k_s values and graphical $-dc/dt$ values are constant showing zero order kinetics with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III). A slight increase in the rate values calculated from the initial slope of the zero order plots at high hexacyanoferrate(III) concentrations might be due to the further oxidation of the intermediate products via

uncatalysed route and due to the acid produced during the course of the reaction. Further oxidation of the intermediate products is also quite clear from the plots where k_s values begin to increase after a certain stage of the reaction. Rate of the uncatalysed reaction can not be measured easily because the intermediate products are formed during the entire course of the reaction and they can not be separated as such. It has been shown in the oxidation of cyclopentanol that further oxidation of the intermediate products proceeds only with alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) and the catalyst does not participate in the reaction⁶. Moreover, it is known that ruthenium is incapable to oxidise aldehydes (which is the case in the present study) and the ketones which have no hydride ion.

Table 2 clearly shows that the reaction shows direct proportionality with respect to ruthenium(VIII) oxide concentrations. At low concentrations of the organic substrate the reaction shows first order kinetics, while at higher concentrations the reaction becomes independent with respect to the organic substrate concentrations (Table 3). Rate of the reaction shows first order kinetics at low hydroxide ion concentrations, it reaches upto a maximum and beyond which further addition of sodium hydroxide retards the reaction rate (Table 4).

After the completion of the reaction, the final oxidation products, viz. propionic acid and butanoic acid were identified in case of propan-1-ol and butan-1-ol, respectively, with the help of paper chromatography technique as well as by the spot-test methods⁷. Rate of the reaction in two different substrates was found to be in the order propan-1-ol < butan-1-ol showing that the rate of oxidation increases with the addition of methyl group in the

TABLE 1 - EFFECT OF VARIATION OF $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]$ ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

(A) $[NaOH] = 0.01 M$, $[Propan-1-ol] = 0.10 M$, $[RuO_4] = 1.21 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 1.00 M$								
$[K_3Fe(CN)_6] (\times 10^3 M)$	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	7.00	8.00
$k_s (\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$	4.02	4.42	4.60	5.05	5.35	5.55	6.05	6.55
$-dc/dt (\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$	4.00	4.55	4.70	5.00	5.30	5.50	6.00	6.50
(B) $[NaOH] = 0.10 M$, $[Butan-1-ol] = 0.10 M$, $[RuO_4] = 1.21 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\mu = 1.00 M$								
$[K_3Fe(CN)_6] (\times 10^3 M)$	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	7.00	8.00
$k_s (\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$	5.82	6.15	6.45	6.75	7.00	7.52	8.00	8.45
$-dc/dt (\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$	5.95	6.20	6.40	6.70	7.00	7.40	7.90	8.40

TABLE 2 - EFFECT OF VARIATION OF $[RuO_4]$ ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

(A) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH] = 0.10 M$, $[Propan-1-ol] = 0.10 M$, $\mu = 1.00 M$								
$[RuO_4] (\times 10^3 M)$	0.24	0.48	0.72	0.97	1.21	1.70	2.20	2.42
$k_s (\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$	0.92	1.76	2.65	3.55	4.55	6.25	8.10	8.90
$-dc/dt (\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$	0.90	1.80	2.70	3.60	4.50	6.20	8.00	8.80
(B) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH] = 0.20 M$, $[Butan-1-ol] = 0.10 M$, $\mu = 1.00 M$								
$[RuO_4] (\times 10^3 M)$	0.24	0.48	0.72	1.21	1.45	1.81	2.05	2.42
$k_s (\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$	1.09	2.14	3.30	5.30	6.62	8.07	9.00	10.38
$-dc/dt (\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$	1.10	2.10	3.20	5.30	6.40	8.00	9.00	10.50

TABLE 3 - EFFECT OF VARIATION OF ORGANIC SUBSTRATE ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

(A) $[K_2Fe(CN)_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH] = 0.10 M$, $[RuO_4] = 1.21 \times 10^{-6} M$, $\mu = 1.00 M$								
[Propan-1-ol] ($\times 10^3 M$)	0.20	2.00	6.00	8.00	10.00	12.00	14.00	18.00
k_2 ($\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$)	0.70	1.40	3.50	3.95	4.54	5.05	5.45	6.20
$-dc/dt$ ($\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$)	0.75	1.50	3.40	4.00	4.50	5.00	5.50	6.25
(B) $[K_2Fe(CN)_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH] = 0.30 M$, $[RuO_4] = 1.21 \times 10^{-6} M$, $\mu = 1.00 M$								
[Butan-1-ol] ($\times 10^3 M$)	2.00	4.00	6.00	8.00	10.00	12.00	14.00	16.00
k_2 ($\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$)	1.55	2.35	3.25	3.50	4.10	4.45	4.75	5.25
$-dc/dt$ ($\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$)	1.60	2.40	3.20	3.55	4.00	4.40	4.80	5.20

TABLE 4 - EFFECT OF VARIATION OF $[OH^-]$ IONS ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

(A) $[K_2Fe(CN)_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Propan-1-ol] = 0.10 M, $[RuO_4] = 1.21 \times 10^{-6} M$, $\mu = 1.00 M$										
[NaOH] ($\times 10^3 M$)	0.50	0.70	1.00	2.00	3.00	5.00	7.00	10.00	20.00	30.00
k_2 ($\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$)	3.33	5.00	6.99	10.82	9.57	7.07	5.77	4.42	3.01	2.50
$-dc/dt$ ($\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$)	3.23	4.85	6.80	10.80	9.50	7.20	5.70	4.55	2.90	2.50
(B) $[K_2Fe(CN)_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Butan-1-ol] = 0.10 M, $[RuO_4] = 1.21 \times 10^{-6} M$, $\mu = 1.00 M$										
[NaOH] ($\times 10^3 M$)	0.50	0.80	1.00	2.00	4.00	6.00	10.00	15.00	20.00	30.00
k_2 ($\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$)	2.70	4.80	8.32	12.48	10.40	8.32	5.82	4.99	4.64	4.08
$-dc/dt$ ($\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1}$)	2.78	4.90	8.20	12.50	10.20	8.20	5.95	5.00	4.50	4.00

molecule. It has been confirmed from the electronic spectral studies that out of many species, $RuO_4(OH)_2^{2-}$ is the only reactive and stable species of RuO_4 in alkaline medium^{8,9} which is given by the following equilibrium,

Thus one might assume $RuO_4(OH)_2^{2-}$ as the only reactive species of ruthenium(viii) oxide in alkaline medium.

On the basis of the experimental results the oxidation of alcohols can be described following Scheme 1.

Thus according to Scheme 1, $RuO_4(OH)_2^{2-}$ with the substrate molecule forms the complex C_2 . At this stage the hydride ion transfer takes place¹⁰⁻¹² and this complex slowly decomposes into a ruthenium(viii) hydride species and a carbonium ion. In the subsequent fast steps, carbonium ion gives rise to the final oxidation products. while the ruthenium(viii) hydride species gets oxidised into the original $RuO_4(OH)_2^{2-}$ species. From Scheme 1 at steady state condition the final rate law might be given as

$$V_i = - \frac{d[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}}{dt} = \frac{2 k_1 k_2 K [Ru^{VIII}]_T [S] [OH^-]}{k_2 + [OH^-] \{k_2 K + k_{-1} K [OH^-] + k_1 K [S] + k_{-1}\}} \quad (1)$$

Scheme 1

where, $R=CH_2CH_3$ for propan-1-ol and $R=CH_2CH_2CH_3$ for butan-1-ol.

Equation (1) clearly explains direct proportionality of the reaction rate with respect to ruthenium(viii) oxide concentrations. The nature shown by the substrate and OH^- ions are also quite clear.

At very low concentrations of the substrate and $[OH^-]$ ions, the inequality

$$k_2 \gg [OH^-] \{k_2 K + k_{-1} K [OH^-] + k_1 K [S] + k_{-1}\}$$

may be assumed to hold valid and the equation (1) reduces to

$$V_t = \frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}}{dt} = 2k_1 K [\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_T [\text{S}] [\text{OH}^-] \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) clearly explains first order kinetics with respect to the substrate and hydroxide ions at their low concentrations as observed experimentally. Direct proportionality of the reaction rate with respect to ruthenium(VIII) oxide is also clear. At higher concentrations of the substrate and hydroxide ions the reverse inequality

$$k_2 \ll [\text{OH}^-] \{k_2 K + k_{-1} K [\text{OH}^-] + k_1 K [\text{S}] + k_{-1}\}$$

will hold good and in this case equation (1) reduces to

$$V_t = -\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}}{dt} = \frac{2k_1 k_2 K [\text{Ru}^{\text{VIII}}]_T [\text{S}]}{k_2 K + k_{-1} K [\text{OH}^-] + k_1 K [\text{S}] + k_{-1}} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) clearly explains zero order kinetics with respect to the substrate at its higher concentrations. It also explains retardation due to OH^- ions at higher alkali concentrations. Direct proportionality of the reaction rate with respect to ruthenium(VIII) oxide even upto its many fold variation in concentration is also explained by this equation.

Further validity of the rate law might be made by plotting $1/V_t$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $1/[\text{S}]$. The straight lines with positive intercepts at $1/V_t$ axes clearly indicate the validity of the rate law (1) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. (A, B) Plots of $1/(-dc/dt)$ vs $[\text{comp}]$ (Table 3); (C, D) plots of $1/(-dc/dt)$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$ (Table 4); (A, C) propan-1-ol, and (B, D) butan-1-ol.

The k_2 values calculated from the intercepts of $1/V_t$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$ plots (Figs 1A and B) come out to be 1.21×10^{-3} and 1.45×10^{-3} for propan-1-ol and butan-1-ol, respectively. Again from the slopes of

$1/V_t$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]$, the values of $K_1 k$ (where, $K_1 = k_{-1}/k_1$) come out to be 51.65 and 82.64 for propan-1-ol and butan-1-ol, respectively (Figs. 1C and D). The values calculated from different methods also verify the validity of rate law (1) and the proposed mechanism.

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Kinetics of Oxidation of some 4-Piperidones by Cerium(IV)

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THE Use of Ce^{IV} as an oxidant has been the subject of several publications¹⁻⁷. However, to our knowledge, no systematic investigation of the kinetics of oxidation of 4-piperidones by Ce^{IV} has been carried out. The present study is an attempt in this direction.